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Challenges and Innovations in Financial Management of Public Health in India: A Focus on the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM)

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Abstract:

Financial management in India's public health sector has historically faced significant challenges, particularly during the implementation of the Reproductive and Child Health Programme Phase I (RCH-I). The program highlighted the need for more specialized financial practices to address issues such as fund misappropriation, lack of transparency, and inefficient fund utilization. With the introduction of the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), there was a marked improvement in financial management through the employment of management and accounting professionals at various levels. This paper explores the evolution of financial management practices under NRHM, the economic reforms that impacted public health expenditure, and the persistent challenges that hinder achieving the target of 3% GDP allocation to health. It also discusses the systemic issues in fund disbursement and utilization at different levels of government and proposes strategies to enhance transparency and efficiency in the management of public health finances.

Keywords: National Rural Health Mission; Financial Management; Public Health Finances in India.

Introduction

Managing public health finances in India has been one of the most challenging tasks, requiring a high level of transparency and professionalism. Historically, India's financial management of public health has been inadequate, particularly under the Reproductive and Child Health Programme Phase I (RCH-I), which highlighted the need for specialized financial practices at various levels. The challenges were not only due to numerous instances of fund misappropriation but also stemmed from a lack of transparency and proper utilization of funds. Additionally, financial management was hampered by the absence of skilled management and accounting professionals within the system.

The implementation of the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) marked a significant shift, as it employed the services of management and accounting professionals at various levels, thereby easing financial management to some extent. The main approach to financial management under the NRHM included fund allocation, disbursement, utilization, and the submission of utilization certificates, all of which required timely execution.

There has been growing interest in the discussion and analysis of health budgets and expenditures for two primary reasons. First, the economic reforms of the 1990s created a downward trajectory in public health spending, both in terms of the government's budget share and as a proportion of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Before the mid-1980s economic reforms, public health expenditure peaked at 1.6% of GDP and 3.95% of the government's budget. By 2001, these figures had declined to a dismal 0.9% and 2.7%, respectively, and further decreased to 0.8% and 2.4% by 2005. The decline in new investments by the Ministry of Health was particularly troubling, as capital expenditures dropped from a robust 12% in 1986-87 to a mere 4% in 2000-01, with only a slight improvement to 5% in 2004-05.

Second, national data from the National Sample Survey (NSS) of the Government of India indicated a shocking decline of over 30% in the proportion of patients seeking care in public health institutions between 1987 and 1996. This decline in the use of public health facilities was precipitated by the underfunding and subsequent collapse of the public health system during the 1990s. Recognizing this neglect, the United Progressive Alliance (UPA) government, through its Common Minimum Program (CMP), promised to remedy the situation with significantly larger investments in health, beginning with the NRHM.

While health is a state subject in India, with state governments contributing between 80% and 85% of health spending, the central government has substantially increased its contribution to the health budget in recent years,

with an annual increase of 30%. However, despite these efforts, the combined health budget of state and central governments remains less than 1% of GDP. To reach the target of 3% of GDP, both central and state governments would need to triple their budgets. Currently, the central government has shown limited capacity to increase its contribution by about one-third each year, while state governments have shown an annual increase of about one-sixth. With such slow progress, the targeted increase to 3% of GDP remains unrealized.

The problem:

Country had witnessed bad financial management records. The main hurdles at initial stages such as many divisions in MOHFW involved in fund transfer and too many budget heads resulted in fund transfer delayed and protracted at all levels. Financial and administrative powers concentrated at the top in almost all States/Districts, Undue (and often counterproductive) dependence on revenue administration at the cost of health administration and low absorption capacity within the system. There was also no skill set within the system for financial management and the reporting structure was in disarray. Proper accounting systems were not in place and financial management conferences unheard of. Financial management even at GOI level restricted to sending funds and waiting for UCs. To end this financial management group (FMG) constituted. Key features of FMG were the concept of flexi pool, single nodal for point of release, accounting, and collection of utilization and audit reports. Under the FMG, personnel trained to accounts related issues. Funds provided under different heads and required to be expending on the prescribed norms. Such FMG was incorporated after the failures of RCH-I and suggest means for RCH-II and extended to cover NRHM. Double accounting systems introduced from the National level to State level, further up to district, and sub district levels. With accounts professional in position at all level could make things easier but such professionals also depended upon the timely disbursement and submission of utilization reports by the authorities (Agrawal, 2007). One of the central pillars of the corrected architecture of the health sector that the NRHM intended to achieve was improved health sector management. The NRHM had five core strategies that address this dimension. One was the creation of the integrated district and state health societies as measure of horizontal integration and convergence, better governance and participatory decision-making. The second in the induction of a number of contractual staff with management skills – program management, data management and financial management. A third was the building up of the state level institutions. The directorates of health services, the state program management units of the registered societies, the SIHFW or equivalent, the state health systems resource center and a autonomous body or empowered cell for management of procurement and another for civil works were some of the institutions that needed to be created or strengthened. These many bodies were not necessarily duplications. Rather they were institutional forms of specific skills and a body of domain specific experience for which an experienced team and an institutional memory need built up. With a clear demarcation of roles and deliverables for each of these institutions, program management made much more effective. However, potentially all of them telescoped into one or two institutions the leadership competencies required were such that separate structures in practice more viable than bringing them all under one roof. Financial Management procedures improved. One major step forward was the use of e-transfer for funds up to the districts. The other was the increase in accounting staff under contractual appointment at the state, district, and block level. The financial powers delegated adequately to the districts, MOICs and various committees. The main components of financial management under NRHM were coordination among different agencies, establishments of new procedures for accounting and ensuring that institutions function accordingly to financial management group (FMG) guidelines. Accounting under NRHM found to be involved with the process of recording the financial transactions in a systematic manner and preparing summarized reports. The accounting process under NRHM thus was inclusive of identification of transaction, recording, classifying, summarizing, analyzing, and reporting the transaction. The accounting tools used under NRHM was Ledger book, Assets books, Cashbooks, Bankbooks, Credit vouchers, Debit vouchers, Sales books, Purchase books, Receipts, Bills.

NRHM could be an overarching framework which could encompass all interventions for health care as well as those for wider determinants of health care. The financing through the NRHM budget head could provide the much-needed funds to the district level to facilitate better health outcome. At the cutting edge i.e. district level, convergent action within the umbrella of the *Zila Parishad* was expected to improve efficiency, effectiveness and outcomes of interventions in the health, women and child, drinking water, sanitation, youth and adolescent, and the school education sector. The framework for local specific decentralized action involving community organizations and PRIs expected to provide a thrust for outcome-based approach to this vital sector.

Looking at the ambitious plan of action under the NRHM, the requirement of funds was likely to be considerable. However, in view of the fact that the current public health expenditure was a paltry 1 percent of the GDP, this quantum jump was indeed timely. Moreover, this was in line with the NCMP which seeks to increase the public health expenditure to 2-3 percent within the next five years The above target however could not be

achieved unless the states also step up their expenditure on health very significantly as they together contribute almost four-fifth of the current expenditure. The fiscal stress under which the states worked too well known elaborated here. The major burden of the additional expenditure could therefore have to be borne by the Central Government at least during the mission period.

It could be the aim of the NRHM to increase the share of central and State Governments on health care from the current 20 – 80 to 40 – 60 sharing in the end. With this in view, it proposed that under the Mission, 100 percent grants provided to States in the remaining period of the X Plan. During the XI Plan period, the states expected to contribute 15 percent to make the share of the Central Government 85 percent. From the XII Plan onwards the relative share of the Centre and the states could be a sustainable 75 – 25 percent. It could however be insured that all along the state expenditure on health increases in real terms and there was no substitution of the state expenditure by Central expenditure. An MOU signed with the states, which sought inter-alia a commitment to increase the state share of expenditure on health, by at least 10 percent every year. The 75-25 arrangement needed to be sustainable to ensure that the gains of the Mission not dissipated and furthered away. Public health infrastructure requires all sustainable financing from the Central Government on a longer period.

As regards costing of additional resource needs, the National Commission on Macro Economics and Health had made a detailed assessment of investment requirements, based on bare minimum standards, costs and needs, largely at Government prices that are 30-50 percent lower than in the private sector. The Commission had recommended additional non-recurring investment of ` 338110 million and a recurring investment of `410060 Million. This expenditure made over a period of five to seven years. The additional recurring requirement worked out for the 7th year. This included health promotion, regulatory systems, enforcement of regulations, human resources for health, training, research, and development, delivery of health care services, and social health insurance. It covered the entire health sector including establishment of new medical colleges, etc., that were not the focus in the National Rural Health mission,

Clearly a major stepping up of financial resources for the health sector was required if the promised 2-3 percent GDP public expenditure on health had to be attained before the end of the 12th Plan (2012). Assuming a 7 percent rate of growth of the economy as also a modest 4-5 percent rate of inflation, the actual financial need at current prices of 2012 could be much higher than the financial needs articulated in terms of the current prices (2005). Given the fact that the public expenditure on the health sector was about 320000 million rupees in 2004-05, the commitment to raise it to 2-3 percent, GDP implies total expenditure on health at current prices to be in the range of ` 600000 to ` 900000 million. This could mean an additional annual commitment of ` 600000 to ` 900000 million in 2012 at current prices. Since the Central Government likely provided a substantial amount of the additional resources need, it was clear that the Central Government share had to go up substantially. Given absorptive capacity in the states and the time it might take, to improve implementation capacity should be fair to assume an annual 30 percent increase in health sector allocations up to 2007-08 and an annual increase of 40 percent from 2009-2010

Framework under NRHM

It was clear from the details of the plan of action under NRHM that very diverse activities had taken up at various levels extending right from the village level to the Central Government level. These activities could also plan and appraised at decentralized level. It was therefore necessary to provide a normative framework under which the activities taken up.

The financial norms under NRHM:

- (i) The approved norms of all the schemes subsumed under the NRHM. These included National Disease Control Programs, all Family Welfare programs and Integrated Disease Surveillance programs;
- (ii) The norms suggested by the National commission on Macro Economics and Health. As the norms of the Commission make it clear, these worked out for Government hospitals and at Government costs. The cost in the non-Governmental sector was likely to higher than what projected by the Commission;
- (iii) Specific financial norms included in the current proposal. These were however broad norms.

Flexibilities might be necessary to take care of the needs and priorities of the states. While approving any proposal included in any State Action Plan, the NPCC, EPC/MSG could rely on the financial norms derived from all the above sources. The States could be encouraged to use these norms conjunctively. For providing quality health care in the rural areas, these would provide a vast menu of options to the States to select. There was no difficulty in using the norms derived from the first source, as they already stood approved. Specific approval would be required for the norms described in the second and the third parts. The second part pertained

to the norms recommended by the National Commission on Macroeconomics and Health. The Commission had suggested a structure and fund requirement for SHC/PHC/CHC. The norms derived from the NCMH pertained to essential medical interventions. To arrive at the figure of per capita expenditure on health services, the report has worked out the unit cost as well as total cost of each intervention included in the packages for core essential health care services, basic health care services provided at CHC and secondary care services at District Hospital.

The details of the three components were as follows: -

A core package to be made accessible at public cost viz. all vector borne diseases, TB, Leprosy, HIV / AIDS (excluding treatment) and other STDs, childhood diseases, preventive and promotive health education that includes immunization against vaccine preventable diseases, ante-natal and postnatal care of mothers, family welfare, information dissemination on health as well as its determinants. A basic package consisting, in addition to the above, surgery and investment for hypertension, diabetes, respiratory diseases such as asthma and injury. A secondary care package consisting of treatment for vascular diseases, cancer, and mental illness over and above the referrals from the CHCs those needed handled at district hospitals.

The above norms could help in reimbursement to accredited private establishments for taking up these interventions. The Mission could like to adopt these norms. It might however be mentioned here that the costs assessed by NCMH were for government hospitals and facilities. The cost in the private sector was likely to be 30-50 percent higher (as mentioned in the report itself). The Mission Steering Group at the State level could have the authority to increase costs by up to 25 percent for private facilities Any further escalation could require the approval of the National level Mission Steering Group. The norms included in the third part comprise pattern of assistance to states and districts; activities to be taken up under the mission as well as the functional and financial norms under which those activities were to be taken up.

It was necessary to clarify that many of these norms were only indicative. For instance, even though norms for physical construction of health facilities indicated, these could be subject to the physical and financial norms prevalent in that state. If the schedule of rates prevalent in that state indicated a lower or higher cost as compared to the costs prescribed, the state rates could prevail. Similarly, mere inclusion of an activity in the framework did not imply that the states could have to take up that activity. No activity might take up without a clear understanding of its outcome or effect. The accountability framework under the NRHM could ensure that the communities keep a strict control on the cost and quality of the services provided.

Results:

Concurrent audit:

Concurrent audit introduced under NRHM to make house under order. The concurrent audit practiced under NRHM, which involved of handholding at the local level at monthly/Quarterly periodicity to make book keeping qualitatively better resulting in better statutory audit compliance.

State budgetary support to institutions:

NRHM launched to supplement the funds available from State budget and not replace it. RBI data showed that the health budget in almost all states enhanced at satisfactory levels. However, it was required to monitor that most of fund not go towards salary and allowances, institution level patient-centric funds replenished and maintained at optimal level and the waiver of user charges being compensated by hike in State budgetary support to affected institutions?

Management of treasury route fund:

Treasury route funds largely meet salaries of ANMs and FW bureaus. In many states, timely payment of salaries had been a constant problem leading to demoralization of perhaps the most important health functionaries. The main reasons identified as delay in sending allocations from GOI, delayed allocation by the Finance Dept. of the State Govt. to Department of health and FW, delayed allocation of funds by the Dept. of HFW to the Directorate of Health and FW and delayed release of funds from the Directorate to the field.

Banking:

It conceptualized under NRHM that Banks used as a partner providing value added services rather than a banker in the traditional sense and expected to be pro-actively involved in fund-flow. Many States had started e-transfer of funds to their districts; however, full potential of e banking still realized. Sub district level transfers remained the weakest link. It realized that there would be tie-ups at district level with the DHS banker on one side and the Lead Bank & *Grameen Bank* on the other side for faster fund transfer to sub-District levels.

Flexible financing:

The central strategy of this support was the provision of untied funds to every level- to the village health and sanitation committee, to the sub-center, to the PHC, to the CHC and district hospital. Even the strategy of providing a resource envelope to each district and state, which the district/state had to use against an approved plan that it developed, was an unprecedented level of financing flexibility. Financial packages for demand side finance and various forms of risk pooling where money followed the patient were also major strategies declared by the NRHM. The *Janani Suraksha Yojana* was one major, almost overwhelming example of the demand side financing option, so much, so that in many places the NRHM identified with it. However, the challenge of the NRHM able to build more comprehensive packages that ensured allocate efficiencies within the public health system and that addressed equity concerns for the entire range of curative care needs.

Basis of funds flow under NRHM:

A tentative budgetary envelope communicated to all states in the beginning of the year (March/April). The States were required to submit a *NRHM Program Implementation Plan (PIP)* for a financial Year in advance with complete projections of funds required to implement the PIP. The PIPs appraised and approved by National Program Coordination Committee (NPCC) of the MOHFW. GFR provisions practiced for fund release according to which the first tranche (to the extent of 75 percent of PIP) released on submission of utilization certificates on a provisional basis for the funds released during the previous year to a State/UT. The unspent balance might take into account. The second tranche (i.e. the balance 25 percent of the approved budget under the PIP) released after the receipt of audited statements and audited utilization certificates for the previous financial year. Fund Release for RCH flexible pool and mission flexible pool required done by NRHM finance division. All utilization certificates (UCs) pertaining to NRHM/RCH flexible pool were required to be sent to the director (NRHM-Finance). Fund released for immunization and other NDCPs required done by the concerned program divisions themselves. UC for these programs required directly sent to the concerned program divisions.

Funds flow under NRHM

Funds flow under the NRHM was based upon the micro plans, program Implementations Plans (PIPs) and district health action plans which submitted by states and districts annually in advance. The funds routed through two ways- direct funds transfer from the central mission directorate to the state health societies and state treasuries. Generally, state treasuries funds utilized to provide salary to administrative, medical, and paramedical staff and to meet other expenditures. While funds flow under NRHM were utilized for salary to contractual staffs and up gradation of infrastructure, logistics and to meet expenses such as planning, training.

Treasury Route:

Under this route expenses such as salaries of the posts of Auxiliary Nurse Midwife (ANMs) & LHVs, training of ANMs, support to family welfare bureau at state and district levels etc met.

Society route:

Under this route expenses such as expenses for Program implementation, salaries for the contractual employees hired for strengthening of Program implementation under the mission met.

Mechanism of funds transfer:

Funds under NRHM States transferred electronically through real time gross settlement (RTGS) within 24-48 hours. For which states were communicated different codes.

Financial monitoring reports (FMRs):

Financial reporting format specifically developed under the NRHM. It was an almost 10 pages format, which contained almost all information about opening balance, fund received, funds utilized and unspent balance. On examination of the format, it appeared that in general NRHM financial format was inclusive of RCH flexi pool, NRHM flexi pool, SRI. Respectively the 14, 28 and 3 heads of expenditure were countable under those three segments. The FMR under NRHM was inclusive of entire gamut of the NRHM activities and inclusive of purchases, salary, allowances, program management cost under different headings. The cycle of FMR was practiced monthly, quarterly, and yearly in most cases. Statements of funds position, bank statement positions were required submitted quarterly and monthly respectively whereas FMR were required submitted quarterly. It was also mandatory to submit annualized audit report by September of the following year and a consolidated audit report for the Society (including all the programs).

Flow of financial reports:

The FMR usually originated from HSC level by ANMs. ANM usually submit reports related to expenses incurred out of untied funds and other funds. She used to route her reports to the district health society directly or through concerned MOICs. MOICs also required submitting FMR to their district health society. CHC/FRU or other Sub district facilities required to submit their reports to district health society. District health society routed their reports to the state health society and from there they used to be sending to the MOHFW/ Director finance (NRHM). The cycle at sub district level and state level were usually monthly and required completed in time bound manner.

NRHM financial management software:

Web enabled software developed under the NRHM for financial management. However, its success was not adequate similar to RIMS software. Non-availability of broadband, electric supply at different levels restricted its proper usage. The software was single to use and synchronize data with single click.

Financial management group (FMG) under NRHM:

The FMG came into being after RCH-I. It was in place under RCH-II and extended to NRHM. Key features of FMG were to single window for funds release and receipt of UCs, Flexible financing etc. The key functions of FMG were analysis of financial situation of states, training of management professionals and study of funds utilization and generation of FMIS.

“It was extremely uneasy to say that everything was okay with financial management under NRHM as several challenges and drawbacks were evident during the investigation. There was a need to track the fund flow from the district downward as large portions of funds devolved to blocks and below. Under NRHM, funds devolved for *Janani Suraksha Yojana* (JSY) revolving funds maintained and regularly recouped by CHC/PHC, ANM, ASHA, etc. Untied and annual maintenance grants to CHCs/PHCs/Sub-Centers, untied grants to village health and sanitation committees (VHSCs), numerous payments to ASHAs for their services provided for a whole gamut of activities, training needs of ASHA were required to be monitored vigorously”.

Conclusion:

The financial management of public health in India, particularly under the NRHM, has evolved significantly over the years. While the introduction of specialized management and accounting practices has improved the transparency and efficiency of fund utilization, several challenges remain. The historical decline in public health spending as a percentage of GDP and the persistent underfunding of health infrastructure at the state level continue to hinder progress. To meet the ambitious target of increasing public health expenditure to 3% of GDP, it is imperative that both central and state governments substantially increase their contributions. Additionally, the establishment of a robust framework for financial management, including the use of technology for real-time fund transfer and monitoring, is essential for ensuring that the gains made under NRHM are sustained and further expanded. Ultimately, achieving these goals will require a concerted effort from all levels of government, along with the active participation of management professionals, to create a public health system that is both financially sound and capable of meeting the needs of India's diverse population.

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